

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CF/PEI COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Composite material development has been dominated by thermosetting polymer based composites in the past, especially unsaturated polyester and epoxy matrix composites. However, the composite industry has become aware of some deficiencies associated with inferior damage tolerance and hot/wet stability [1-2]. Significant progress has been made in improving the fracture toughness of thermosetting matrix systems, but other problems associated with hot/wet stability are still concerned in practical applications. Awareness of such concerns has led to the development of a new class of engineering materials, continuous fiber composites combined with high performance thermoplastic matrices such as polyetherimide (PEI), polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and polyphenylene sulphide (PPS), etc. With the increasing application of thermoplastic composites, there has been considerable concern about their resistance to environmental conditions [3-5]. Therefore, this study aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the influence of environmental temperature on plain woven and unidirectional fabric reinforced carbon fiber polyetherimide (CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud}) composites through the mechanical performance of the composites with variations in temperature.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Plain woven and unidirectional fabrics were provided by Hyundai Fiber, Korea. PEI films were used as matrix for plain woven and unidirectional fabric reinforced CF/PEI composites. PEI films (ULTEM 1000) were supplied by SABIC Innovative Plastics.

2.2 Preparation of specimens

A rectangular closed mould was used to manufacture CF/PEI composites. The internal dimension of the cavity of the mould was 300 mm × 250 mm. Thirty-two plain woven or unidirectional fabrics were laid with PEI films for film stacking process. Two polyimide films (50µm in thickness) were placed between the stacked sheets and mould plates to facilitate easy release from the tooling surface and ensure smooth laminate surfaces after consolidation. A polyimide film (25µm in thickness) was inserted into the mid-plane of the stacked sheets to produce an initial delamination in the consolidated laminate panels for the mode-I and mode-II interlaminar tests. The stacked sheets were heated to 330°C in 100 minutes, and then consolidated at 330°C for 60 minutes with an applied pressure of 2.5 MPa using a hot press. The laminate was cooled under the pressure to a temperature far below the glass transition temperature of 215°C. After consolidation, laminate panels were cut and ground into standard mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture specimens, in accordance with ASTM D 5528-01 [6] and ESIS [7], respectively, using a diamond saw and a grinding machine. To introduce the load for the DCB specimens, aluminum T-tabs were bonded onto both sides of the specimens at the end of initial delamination, using a high-strength commercial epoxy based adhesive, and the bonding was further secured with aid of screws to prevent bonding failure at elevated temperatures, producing an initial delamination length of 50 mm.

2.3 Interlaminar fracture toughness tests

Mode-I double cantilever beam (DCB) and mode-II end notched flexure (ENF) tests were performed in a temperature range from room temperature (RT, approximately 25°C) to 130°C using an environmental chamber in accordance with ASTM D 5528-01 [6] and ESIS [7], respectively. In the mode-I interlaminar fracture test, Universal testing

machine (UTM, HOUNSFILED, H100K) was operated in displacement control mode at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min with a computer-based data acquisition system. To monitor the position of the delamination front, the sides of the specimens were painted with white correction fluid and marked at 1 mm intervals. Throughout the tests, the load-displacement curve was monitored and the length of delamination was checked at regular intervals using a traveling telescope, which permits optical measurement of delamination length through the front window of the environmental chamber. G_{IC} was evaluated using the modified beam theory method ASTM D 5528-01[6]. Mode-II ENF specimens were tested at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. Experimental compliance calibration [7] was first conducted for individual specimens, then each specimen was continuously loaded until the delamination was arrested beneath the upper loading pin, or the specimen failed in bending. Delamination propagation length was monitored and measured using the traveling telescope. G_{IIC} was evaluated using a method based on the experimental compliance calibration [7].

3 Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows typical load-displacement curves of mode-I interlaminar fracture of CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites at different testing temperatures. For the CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites at room temperature, the load dropped sharply at several points during delamination propagation in the load-displacement curves, followed by a further increase in load. This behaviour has been referred to as “stick-slip” crack propagation [8], accompanying a series of unstable crack propagations and arrests. On the other hand, the load decreased gradually at 130°C, with less tendency for stick-slip behaviour. For both composite systems, the delamination behaviour was highly dependent on environmental temperature, and the delamination propagation became more stable with increasing temperature. Four different initiation toughness values, $G_{IC,ini}$ for the CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites, were determined from the load-displacement curves, which are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively. The $G_{IC,ini}$ values determined at the deviation from linearity (NL) and those when delamination was visually observed to

initiate on the edge (VIS) have similar values, and they decrease as the temperature increases, while the $G_{IC,ini}$ values calculated from the offset load (5%) by a 5% increase in the initial compliance and the maximum load (MAX) show the reverse trend, but these values were clearly overestimated because delamination had already propagated, with an advance of 4~5mm beyond the initial delamination. Hence, the $G_{IC,ini}$ values determined from the NL and/or VIS points were selected to characterize the initiation of delamination. The initiation toughness ($G_{IC,ini}$) and the propagation toughness ($G_{IC,prop}$) for the interlaminar fracture of the CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, respectively. Both $G_{IC,ini}$ and $G_{IC,prop}$ of CF/PEI_w composites are greater than those of the CF/PEI_{ud} composites. However, both the composites exhibit the same trend that their $G_{IC,ini}$ decreases and $G_{IC,prop}$ increases as the temperature increases from RT to 130°C. The measured $G_{IC,prop}$ values for the CF/PEI_w composites are in good agreement with those reported in the literature at RT and 80°C [9-10], and similar results have been observed for other thermoplastic matrix composites such as CF/PEEK composites.

Fig. 6 shows mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness for delamination initiation, $G_{IIC,ini}$, of the CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites. The plain woven composites exhibited the substantially higher fracture toughness than the unidirectional composites for mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture. The higher toughness was mainly responsible for transverse yarn debonding and the large plastic zone to be developed ahead of the crack tip during delamination due to the intrinsic woven structure of undulating warp yarns [10]. The decrease in $G_{IC,ini}$ and $G_{IC,prop}$ for the composites can be attributed to the weaker fiber/matrix interfacial strength at the elevated temperatures.

Fig.1. Typical load-displacement curves of CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites in mode-I DCB tests at different temperatures.

Fig.3. Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness for delamination initiation, $G_{IC,ini}$, of CF/PEI_w composites at different temperatures.

Fig.2. Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness for delamination initiation, $G_{IC,ini}$, of CF/PEI_{ud} composites at different temperatures.

Fig.4. Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness for delamination initiation, $G_{IC,ini}$, of CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites at different temperatures.

Fig.5. Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness for delamination propagation, $G_{IC,prop}$, of CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites at different temperatures.

Fig.6. Mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness for delamination initiation, $G_{IIc,ini}$, of CF/PEI_w and CF/PEI_{ud} composites at different temperatures.

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